

ISic2832

I.Sicily inscription 2832

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2018.07.17

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Grotta di Fragapane, near the entrance of camera sepolcrale B (lower fr. 1941; upper fr.1950)

Coordinates

37.290161, 13.589661

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory 5756

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. [---]

1. [---]καὶ Ἀγ[άθη]

2. [---]α · μνη[σθη̄][---]

3. [---][ἐγὼ]ἐπικαλοῦμ[αιτὸνλαὸν][---]

4. [---][ἐκτ]ῆς ἐμῆς π[ροικὸςβοηθεῖν][---]

5. [---][τοῖς] πένησι · κα[ιὶὄρφανοῖςτῶν---]

6. Ἰουδ[αίων][---]

Edition: PHI178084

1. [— — — — —] . . [— — — — —]

2. [— — — —] καὶ #⁵⁶ ἄ π [— — —]

3. [— — — —] α #⁵⁶ μ ν η [— — — —]

4. [— —] ἐπικαλουμ [— — — — —]

5. [— — —] ης #⁵⁶ ἐμῆς π [— — —]

6. [— —] πένησι #⁵⁶ κ α [— — — —]

7. vacat Ἰουδ [αι(?)— — —]

8.

Edition: PHI332687

1. [— — — — — — — — — — —]
2. [— — — —] καὶ #⁵⁶ Ἄγ [άθη — —]
3. [— — — —] α #⁵⁶ μνη [σθῆ(?) — —]
4. [έγώ] ἐπικαλοῦμ [αι τὸν λαὸν]
5. [έκ τ]ῆς #⁵⁶ ἐμῆς π[ροικὸς βοη]-
6. [θεῖν] πένησι #⁵⁶ κ,α [ὶ ὀρφανοῖς]
7. vacat Ἰουδ [αίων. vacat]
- 8.

Edition: PHI336054

1. [— —] καὶ Ἄ γ [άθη(?) — — — — — —]
2. [— —] α □ μνη [σθῆ — — — — — —]
3. [έγώ] ἐπικαλοῦμ [αι τὸν λαὸν — —]
4. [έκ τ] ῆς □ ἐμῆς π [ροικὸς(?) βοηθεῖν]
5. [τοῖς] πένησι □ κα [ὶ ὀρφανοῖς(?) τῶν]
6. Ἰουδ [αίων]
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

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ΜΙΝ
ΚΑΘΟΥ
ΟΜΗΟ
ΤΕΝΗΟΝ
ΟΜΗΟΝ

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Photo J. Prag, courtesy Museo Archeologico Regionale P. Griffo, Agrigento